

**90-day Brake Dust Sub-chronic Inhalation Toxicology Study (Nose-only) in the Rat
(CiToxLAB study code: 15/248-212P; Fraunhofer ITEM Study No.: 02G16015)
Pathology Phase-Report, Draft 1**

Histopathology of the Respiratory Tract

The protocol organs included all respiratory tract organs, i.e. the nasal cavity, nasopharynx, larynx, trachea, lung and lung-associated lymph nodes. These organs/tissues were examined in all animals, i.e. 4 rats per group and necropsy subgroup. Additional organs/tissues were only examined if macroscopic findings were present.

1. 45 day interim sacrifice

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

(Multi)focal very slight (minimal) alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden (Brake dust, Titanium-dioxide and Chrysotile groups) or fiber-laden (Crocidolite and Amosite groups) macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 4/4 rats each of group 2 (Brake dust low), 3 (Brake dust mid), 4 (Brake dust high), 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high) as well as in 3/4 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; 1/4 rats: slight degree). And correspondingly, 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight) showed multifocal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. In group 1 (Clean air control), alveolar histiocytosis could not be observed. Very slight (multi)focal occurrence of multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells was seen in a single rat of group 7 (Chrysotile high) and in 3/4 and 4/4 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite), respectively.

(Multi)focal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was exclusively observed in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite, all very slight) and 9 (Amosite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight). The same was true for multifocal alveolar/interstitial (intraseptal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells, which occurred in all rats of group 8 (3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (all slight). The incidence of (multi)focal perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration ranged between 1/4 rats per group in all Brake dust groups and in the Chrysotile low group (all very slight), 2/4 rats per group in the Chrysotile high group (all very slight) and 4/4 rats per group in the Crocidolite and Amosite group (each 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight). In addition, a single rat of the Titanium-dioxide group showed focal very slight perivascular mononuclear cell infiltration and 1/4 rats of group 9 (Amosite) revealed focal very slight pleural (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration. As a further exposure-related finding, focal or multifocal very slight microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 2/4 and 4/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and

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7 (Chrysotile high), respectively, while all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed slight multifocal microgranulomas.

(Multi)focal adaptive bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was diagnosed as spontaneous finding in a single control animal (very slight), and as exposure-related finding in 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), 8 (Crocidolite; all slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight).

Multifocal very slight interstitial fibrosis was observed in all rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) only. In addition, single rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low), 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed very slight or slight focal pleural fibrosis.

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control), while all rats of group 2 – 4 (Brake dust low, -mid and -high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide) as well as 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) were scored with Wagner grade 2 (a few macrophages present within terminal bronchioles and alveoli). The remaining 2 animals of group 6 and all rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high) received Wagner grade 3 (bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia present and more conspicuous macrophages and inflammatory cells). Wagner grade 4 (presence of minimal interstitial fibrosis) was applied to 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) only.

b) Spontaneous findings

Further spontaneous findings included very slight or slight focal neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia and lymphoma/leukemia cell infiltration (s. below). These changes affected single animals of different groups.

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of single animals from group 2-6 and 9, (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages could be observed. In addition, the LALN of single or up to 2/4 rats of most of these groups revealed slight lymphoid hyperplasia.

Other organs

In a single animal of group 8 (Crocidolite; animal no.: 8002), a malignant lymphoma was diagnosed as the only neoplasm in the current sacrifice group. Lymphoma cell infiltrates were observed in the larynx, lung, LALN and nasal cavity, as well as in the macroscopically enlarged liver, iliac lymph node (lymph node, NOS) and spleen. This neoplasm is also considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment of the animal.

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No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single rats of 3 exposure groups showed spontaneous very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration. This finding was also observed in the trachea of 1/4 and 3/4 rats of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and 4 (Brake dust high), respectively.

2. 90 day sacrifice

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

(Multi)focal very slight (minimal) alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden (Brake dust, Titanium-dioxide and Chrysotile groups) or fiber-laden (Crocidolite and Amosite groups) macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 4/4 rats each of group 2 (Brake dust low), 3 (Brake dust mid), 4 (Brake dust high), 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high) as well as in 3/4 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; 1/4 rats: slight degree). Multifocal slight alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages was seen in all (4/4 rats each group) rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite), respectively, while 2/4 animals of group 1 (Clean air control) showed focal very slight or slight alveolar histiocytosis. In addition, single animals each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed very slight multifocal accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages in the BALT (bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue). (Multi)focal occurrence of multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells was observed in a single rat of group 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; all very slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight).

(Multi)focal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was diagnosed in a single rat of group 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite, 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight). The incidence of very slight (multi)focal perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration ranged between 2/4 rats per group in group 2 (Brake dust low), 3 (Brake dust mid), 4 (Brake dust high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide), 3/4 rats per group each in group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high) and 4/4 animals per group each in group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite). Very slight (multi)focal alveolar/interstitial (intraseptal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells occurred in a single rat of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) and in 3/4 and 4/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), respectively, while all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed alveolar/interstitial inflammatory cell infiltration at a slight degree of severity.

As a further exposure-related finding, multifocal very slight microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 4/4 rats each of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile

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high), while all rats (4/4 each group) of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed slight multifocal microgranulomas.

(Multi)focal very slight adaptive bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was observed as exposure-related finding in single animals each of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and 4 (Brake dust high) and in 4/4 rats each of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), while 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed this change at a slight degree of severity.

Multifocal interstitial fibrosis was seen in 2/4 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight). In addition, a single rat of group 9 (Amosite) showed very slight focal pleural fibrosis.

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control), while all rats of group 2 – 4 (Brake dust low, -mid and -high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide) were scored with Wagner grade 2. Wagner grade 3 was applied to all rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and to 2/4 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high). The remaining 2 animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high) as well as all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) received Wagner grade 4.

b) Spontaneous findings

Incidental findings included very slight focal alveolar hemorrhage in a single control animal and very slight or slight focal neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia in single rats each of group 4 (Brake dust high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide).

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of up to 3/4 animals per group from nearly all particle- or fiber-exposure groups, (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages could be observed. In addition, the LALN of single or up to 2/4 rats of some of these groups revealed slight lymphoid hyperplasia.

Other organs

No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single or up to 2/4 rats of some exposure groups showed very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell or (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration. Very slight or slight focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration was also observed in the trachea of single rats of group 1 (Clean Air Control) and group 8 (Crocidolite).

In the nasal cavity, a single rat of group 9 (Amosite) revealed multifocal very slight hyaline (eosinophilic) droplets of the olfactory epithelium.

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All these findings were considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to particle- or fiber-exposure.

3. 3 months postexposure sacrifice

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

Multifocal very slight (minimal) alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 4/4 rats each of group 2 (Brake dust low), 3 (Brake dust mid), 4 (Brake dust high), 5 (Titanium-dioxide), 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), while 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed multifocal slight alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. Spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregation (alveolar histiocytosis) was diagnosed in a single control animal (group 1). The incidences of (multi)focal very slight to slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages in the BALT (bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue) were increased as compared to the previous sacrifices: 2/4 each (group 2 and 4), 3/4 (group 3) and 4/4 each (group 5 - 9). Multifocal multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells were observed exclusively in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight). (Multi)focal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was diagnosed in a single rat of group 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite, 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight). The incidences of (multi)focal perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration were 3/4 in group 2 (2/4 very slight, 1/4 slight), 2/4 each in group 4 (all very slight) and group 7 (1/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 4/4 each in group 6 (all very slight), 8 (1/4 very slight, 3/4 slight) and 9 (2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), respectively. Very slight (multi)focal alveolar/interstitial (intra-septal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells occurred in 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and in 4/4 animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high), while all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed alveolar/interstitial inflammatory cell infiltration at a slight degree of severity. In addition, single animals of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and 7 (Chrysotile high) showed very slight focal pleural (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration.

As a further exposure-related finding, multifocal very slight microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 3/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and in 4/4 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high). All rats (4/4 each group) of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed slight multifocal microgranulomas.

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(Multi)focal very slight bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was observed in single animals each of group 1 (Clean air control) and 5 (Titanium dioxide), in 2/4 males of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and in 4/4 rats each of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), while 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed this change at a slight degree of severity.

(Multi)focal interstitial fibrosis was seen in a single male of group 2 (Brake dust low; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), 8 (Crocidolite; all slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight), respectively. In addition, single rats of group 2 (Brake dust low), 5 (Titanium dioxide), 7 (Chrysotile high) and 8 (Crocidolite), as well as 2/4 males of group 9 (Amosite) showed very slight focal pleural fibrosis.

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control), while all rats of group 2 – 4 (Brake dust low, -mid and -high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide) were scored with Wagner grade 2. Wagner grade 3 was applied to all rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), while all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite), respectively, received Wagner grade 4.

b) Spontaneous findings

A single rat of group 3 (Brake dust mid) showed slight focal neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia as a further incidental finding.

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of 2/4 to 4/4 animals per group from the particle-exposure groups 2-7, (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle-laden macrophages could be observed, while 4/4 rats each of the fiber-exposure groups 8 (Crocidolite; all slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), respectively, revealed (multi)focal accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. In addition, the LALN of single or up to 2/4 rats of some of these groups revealed slight lymphoid hyperplasia.

Other organs

No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single or up to 2/4 rats of the control group and some exposure groups showed very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell or (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration. In addition, single animals of some groups revealed (multi)focal very slight to slight subepithelial (agonal) hemorrhage.

In the nasal cavity, up to 3/4 rats per group showed multifocal very slight to slight (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the respiratory and/or olfactory epithelium. The incidence of this age-related change was increased as compared to the previous examination subsets. In addition,

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single rats of some groups showed very slight focal mucous cell hyperplasia, slight hyperplasia of the NALT (nasal mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue) and (multifocal) very slight subepithelial (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration.

In the trachea, single animals of most groups revealed very slight focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration.

As a correlate to macroscopic observations, control animal no. 1021 showed a severe diffuse purulent (suppurative) inflammation of the prostate and rat no. 4023 (Brake dust high) was affected by a severe focal subcutaneous abscess.

All these findings were considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment.

4. 6 months postexposure sacrifice

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

(Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 3/4 rats of group 2 (Brake dust low; all very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 3 (Brake dust mid; all very slight), 4 (Brake dust high; all very slight), 5 (Titanium-dioxide; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight), 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) and 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), while 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 1/4 very slight, 3/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight) showed multifocal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. There was no occurrence of spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregation (alveolar histiocytosis) in the clean air control group (group 1). The incidences of (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages in the BALT (bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue) were 1/4 each in group 2 and 3, 3/4 each in group 4 and 5, and 4/4 each in group 6 - 9. Multifocal multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells were exclusively observed in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight).

Multifocal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was diagnosed in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite, 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight) only.

The incidences of (multi)focal very slight perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration were 1/4 each in group 2 - 5 (all very slight), 3/4 in group 7 (all very slight) and 4/4 each in group 6 (2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), 8 (all very slight) and 9 (2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), respectively.

(Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial (intra-septal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells occurred in 2/4 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; all very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 6 (Chrysotile

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low; all very slight), 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight). In addition, single animals of group 1 (Clean air control) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide) showed very slight focal interstitial or pleural (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration.

As a further exposure-related finding, multifocal very slight microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and in 4/4 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high). All rats (4/4 each group) of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed slight multifocal microgranulomas.

(Multi)focal very slight bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was observed in single animals each of group 2 (Brake dust low), 4 (Brake dust high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide), as well as in 2/4 males of group 3 (Brake dust mid). In group 6 (Chrysotile low; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight), 7 (Chrysotile high; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), 8 (Crocidolite; all slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight), 4/4 rats each were affected by this change at a very slight to slight degree of severity. Multifocal interstitial fibrosis was seen in a single male of group 6 (Chrysotile low; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight), respectively. In addition, 2/4 males of group 9 (Amosite) showed very slight or slight focal pleural fibrosis.

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control) and to 1/4 males of group 2 (Brake dust low), while 3/4 rats each of group 2 and 5 (Titanium-dioxide), as well as 4/4 rats each of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and 4 (Brake high) were scored with Wagner grade 2. Wagner grade 3 was applied to a single rat of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) and to 3/4 and 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), respectively. All rats from group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) as well as 1/4 and 2/4 animals of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), respectively, received Wagner grade 4.

b) Spontaneous findings

Single rats each of group 3 (Brake dust mid), 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed slight focal chondro-osseous metaplasia as an incidental finding.

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of 1/4 to 4/4 animals per group from the particle-exposure groups 2-7, (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle-laden macrophages could be observed, while 4/4 rats each of the fiber-exposure groups 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) revealed multifocal accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. In addition, the LALN of single or up to 2/4 rats of some of these groups revealed slight lymphoid hyperplasia.

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Other organs

No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single or up to 2/4 rats of the control group and some exposure groups showed very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration. In addition, up to 2/4 rats of two groups revealed focal slight subepithelial (agonal) hemorrhage and a single rat of group 2 (Brake dust low) showed slight focal dilatation of the submucosal glands.

In the nasal cavity, single rats of the control, Brake dust mid and both Chrysotile groups as well as 3/4 and 2/4 rats of the Crocidolite and Amosite exposure groups, respectively, showed multifocal very slight to slight (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the olfactory epithelium. Very slight multifocal (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the respiratory epithelium were only observed in 2/4 animals of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite). In addition, single rats of some groups showed very slight focal corpora amylacea within the olfactory epithelium, (multi)focal very slight to slight mucous cell hyperplasia and focal very slight subepithelial (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration. Slight hyperplasia of the NALT (nasal mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue) was observed in single animals of most particle-exposure groups and in 3/4 rats of group 9 (Amosite).

In the trachea, single animals of different groups revealed very slight or slight focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration.

All these findings were considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment.